

Therefore the production of nascent hydrogen and its activity are the function of the ionisation potential of the particular metal. The following table records the second ionisation potential (e) and the ionic radii (r) of Mg, Zn and Cd from Pauli.

TABLE II

Metal.	e .	r .	e/r .
Zn	17.89 volts	0.74Å	24.2
Mg	14.96	0.65	23.0
Cd	16.84	0.97	17.3

It is seen from the above table that the value of e/r for these metals are in the order of Zn-Mg and Cd, which is also the order of reduction of V_2O_5 in HCl by these metals. Therefore it can be concluded that the nascent activity of hydrogen from different sources is a function of ionisation potential and the ionic radii of the metals generating the hydrogen. e/r has the dimensions of force and may be termed "field intensity".

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USE OF THIAZOLIDONES AND 5-AMINOTHIAZOLIDONES AS ANALYTICAL REAGENTS FOR COPPER AND SILVER

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In course of our investigations on "thiazolidone compounds", it was considered of interest to study all their possible applications in analytical procedures, viz., for the estimation of silver (Das and Rout, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 16). Another compound of the same series has been examined here for its use in the estimation of copper. One of another type of thiazolidone derivatives, viz., 5-amino-2-*p*-nitrophenyl-imino-4-thiazolidone, has also been studied for the estimation of silver.

Estimation of Copper.—The reagent, 2-*p* tolylimino-4-thiazolidone, was prepared by refluxing *p*-tolylthiourea and monochloroacetic acid in absolute alcohol using anhydrous sodium acetate as the condensing agent. Stock solutions of copper sulphate were prepared and were estimated by the iodimetric method. The reagent being insoluble in water, a solution of the reagent in minimum volume of alcohol was employed.

To a known volume of the standard $CuSO_4$ solution, maintained at pH 5.2 by adding 100 c.c. NaAc-HAc buffer, an excess of the warm alcoholic solution of the reagent (2%) was added dropwise with constant stirring till complete precipitation. The complex formed was slightly warmed for about 5 minutes on a water-bath and allowed to stay overnight. Some of the reagent came down along with the complex that had precipitated. This could not, however, be removed by any of the solvents or solvent mixtures without affecting the weight of the complex. Hence, the precipitate was

filtered through a Whatman 42 filter paper. The precipitate was next dried and ignited in a tared porcelain crucible to a constant weight.

TABLE I

CuO calc.	CuO found.	Error.
0.0976 g.	0.0976 g.	± 0
0.0936	0.0934	-0.0002 g.
0.0858	0.0856	-0.0002

The complex when analysed gives the following results: C, 50.33% ; H, 3.42% ; N, 11.46% ; Cu, 13.23%. These point to the molecular formula given below for the complex. The proposed formula $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2$ requires C, 50.68 ; H, 3.80 ; N, 11.82 ; Cu, 13.39%.

Estimation of Silver.—The reagent, 5-amino-2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone, was prepared by the cleavage of the azo group in 5-phenylazo-2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone, which was prepared by coupling diazotised aniline with 2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone.

Stock solutions of the salt (AgNO_3) were prepared and were estimated by titrating with standard thiocyanate solutions using ferric alum as indicator. The amino compound being insoluble in water, its alcoholic solution was used.

To the AgNO_3 solution (containing 0.5966 g. AgNO_3), maintained at p_{H} 5.2 (by adding 50 c.c. of acetate buffer), 0.95 g. of the reagent in 15 c.c. warm alcohol was added dropwise with constant stirring. The complex formed was warmed at 60° for about 10 minutes, kept overnight and filtered through a previously weighed (Gooch) No. 4 crucible. The precipitate was washed with 20% warm alcohol. The complex was dried at 105° and weighed.

TABLE II

Ag present in soln.	Wt. of the complex calculated on the basis of the formula proposed.	Wt. of the complex found.
0.05966 g.	0.1263 g.	0.1260 g.
0.05966	0.1263	0.1259
0.05966	0.1263	0.1261

Composition of the Silver Complex.—A known amount of the silver complex was taken in a weighed porcelain crucible and heated till the organic contents were burnt away. The crucible was then heated to red heat for about half an hour, cooled and the contents weighed.

TABLE III

Ag present in soln.	Wt. of complex.	Ag found.
0.0312 g.	0.1042 g.	0.0310 g.
0.0292	0.0974	0.0289

The above results lead to the conclusion that the silver complex formed will be formulated as $\text{Ag}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S})$.

The complex when analysed gives the following results: C, 29.67% ; H, 1.68% ; N, 15.23% ; Ag, 29.78%. These point to the formula given above for the complex. The proposed formula requires C, 30.08 ; H, 1.94 ; N, 15.59 ; Ag, 30.08%.

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BEHAVIOUR OF CHLORONITROBENZENES WITH HYDRAZINE AND HYDRAZINE DERIVATIVES: HYDRAZOBENZENES

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Interaction between a benzene derivative having a reactive halogen atom, viz., picryl chloride, and phenylhydrazine was employed by Fischer (*Annalen*, 1887, 190, 132) to prepare 2:4:6-trinitrohydrazobenzene. Subsequently, by reacting benzene derivatives having a labile halogen atom with phenylhydrazine and substituted phenylhydrazines, Willgerodt and collaborators (*Ber.*, 1891, 24, 1661 ; *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1882, ii, 37, 351 ; 1891, 43, 490 ; 1891, 44, 72, 452) obtained 2'-chloro-, 3'-chloro- and 4'-chloro-2:4:6-trinitro-, -2:4-dinitro-, 3'-chloro-, 4'-chloro- and 4'-bromo-2:4-dinitrohydrazobenzenes. Werner and co-workers (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 3266) prepared 2:4:2'-trinitro-, 2:4:3'-trinitro- and 2:4:4'-trinitrohydrazobenzenes.

Giusa and co-workers (*Gazzetta*, 1918, 48, 8 ; 1921, 51, 307 ; 1922, 52, 346 ; 1923, 53, 165 ; *Atti R. Acad. Lincei*, 1918, v, 27, 379) and Mangini (*Gazzetta*, 1935, 65, 1191) prepared by substitution of a labile nitro group some derivatives of hydrazobenzene, such as, 5-chloro-2:4-dinitro-, 5-bromo-2:4-dinitro-, 5-chloro-2:4'-dinitro-, -4:6-dinitro-3-methyl-, -2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-, 5-chloro-2:4'-dinitro-, 4:6-dinitro-2':3-dimethyl- and 4:6-dinitro-3:4'-dimethylhydrazobenzenes.

During the present investigations some substituted hydrazobenzenes have been prepared by keeping polynitro compounds having a labile halogen atom with phenylhydrazine (1:2) in alcohol at room temperature (15°-20°) for 3 to 4 days. 3-Chloro-4:6-dinitro-, 2-chloro-4:6-dinitro-, 2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-, 4:6-dinitro-3-methyl-, 4:6-dinitro-2-methyl-, 2:4:6-trinitro-3-methylhydrazobenzenes have been obtained from 1-chloro-3-bromo-4:6-dinitro-, 1:2-dichloro-4:6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-4:6-dinitro-3-methyl-, 1-chloro-4:6-dinitro-2-methyl- and 1-chloro-2:4:6-trinitro-3-methyl-benzenes and phenylhydrazine in this way.